

Event metadata

Event title	Multivariate integration of multi-omics data with mixOmics
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	06/03/2024
Time of event	1pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Multi-omics data (eg. transcriptomics, proteomics) collected from the same set of biospecimens or individuals is a powerful way to understand the underlying molecular mechanisms of a biological system.</p> <p>mixOmics, a popular R package, integrates omics data from a wide range of sources into a single, unified view making it easier to explore and reveal interactions between omics layers. It overcomes many of the challenges of multi-omic data integration arising from data that are complex and large, with few samples (<50) and many molecules (>10,000), and generated using different technologies.</p> <p>Prof Kim-Anh Lê Cao, head of the mixOmics team, is delivering this webinar to outline the different methods implemented in mixOmics and how statistical data integration is defined in this context. She will demonstrate how these approaches are applied to analysis of different multi-omics studies and outline the latest methodological developments in this area. From a study of human newborns, to multi-omics microbiomes, and multi-omics in single cells, these examples illustrate how mixOmics is used to perform variable selection and identify a signature of omics markers that characterise a specific phenotype or disease status.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/mixomics

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Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Omics http://edamontology.org/topic_3391 Multiomics Data integration
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists, bioinformaticians and anyone with an interest in exploration and integration of multiomics biological datasets.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outline the different methods implemented in mixOmics and how statistical data integration is defined in this context. • List examples of how these approaches are applied to analysis of different multi-omics studies
Speakers	Prof Kim-Anh Lê Cao, Director of Melbourne Integrative Genomics, School of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Melbourne.
Related material	None